

Example layers for the ReLive crop yield estimation map using an Estonian example set of agricultural land parcels

Abbreviations for the used data sources:

“OSM” – Open Street Map;

“EC” – European Commission;

“ELB” – Estonian Land Board;

“ARIB” – Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Bureau;

“Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data” - the Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite mission.

Fig. 1. The usual map view to the example area in Estonia which is composed mainly of cropland, meadows and forest land use class.

Source: OSM

Fig. 2. The shaded land relief map with the contours of height. This will be useful for estimating differences in fertility of soils and eventually the crop yield on flat regions vs areas with varying relief.

Source: ELB

Fig. 3. The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). Red corresponds to the cropland areas in which during the management bare soil has been recently exposed.

Source: ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 4. The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) – applied is the mask of land of low height vegetation (i.e. not forest nor high bushes). Inhomogenities which show up on arbitrary land parcel give a hint of possible differences in soil fertility, managing practices during the time - eventually the crop yield.

Source: ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 5. The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) – applied is the mask of land of low height vegetation. The yellow-green overlay shows the areas of permanent grasslands among all managed land. The layer is published under the “Copernicus Land Monitoring Service”.

Source: EC, ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 6. The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) – applied is the mask of land of low height vegetation. The foggy-green overlay shows the buffer zones of reach of natural enemies of crop damaging insects to field plots. Calculated and published by ARIB.

Source: ARIB, ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 7. The false color image of (Near Infrared, NDVI, Red) – applied is the mask of land of low height vegetation. It is derived from before mentioned NDVI index, but is more useful in highlighting the inhomogenities which show up on arbitrary land parcel give a hint of possible differences in soil fertility, managing practices during the time - eventually the crop yield. The brighter yellow areas show all-healthy crops, the blue regions correspond to recently exposed bare soil. The purple regions inside any parcel show areas with partial cover of grass or crop.

Source: ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 9. The vegetation water stress index NDPI. The yellower areas correspond to wetter, whereas the bluer areas to dryer areas on field plots.

Source: ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18

Fig. 10. The false color image of (NDPI, NDVI, Blue). It is derived from before mentioned indices of NDVI and NDPI, but is more useful in highlighting the areas of bare soil which show up on arbitrary land parcel, giving a hint of possible differences in soil fertility, managing practices during the time - eventually the crop yield.

Source: ELB, Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data 2021-06-18